

First Records of Dolichopodidae (Diptera) from Kaluga Region of Russia

I. Ya. Grichanov

All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection
Podbelskogo St. 3
Petersburg-Pushkin, 196608, Russia

E-mail: grichanov@mail.ru

Grichanov I. Ya. First Records of Dolichopodidae (Diptera) from Kaluga Region of Russia. Summary. The faunistic data of the results of collecting dolichopodids (7 species) in the Kaluga Region of Russia during short-term visit (June, 2010) are presented. All species are firstly recorded for the region.

Key words: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, fauna, Russia, Kaluga.

Гричанов И. Я. Первые данные о Dolichopodidae (Diptera) Калужской области, Россия. Резюме. Представлены результаты сборов долихоподид (7 видов) в Калужской области России во время экскурсии автора в июне 2010 г. Все виды впервые отмечаются для области.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, фауна, Россия, Калужская область.

Гричанов І. Я. Перші відомості про Dolichopodidae (Diptera) Калужської області, Росія. Резюме. Наведено результати зборів долихоподид (7 видів) в Калужській області Росії у червні 2010 г. Всі види вперше відмічено для області.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, фауна, Росія, Калузька область.

Introduction

When studying recent Diptera catalogs, I have found that the fauna of the long-legged flies (Dolichopodidae) of Kaluga Region of Russia remained unstudied (Гричанов и Негроров, 1979; Negrobov, 1991; Grichanov, 2003–2010). This paper presents the new records in detail. All species are widespread across the Palearctic Region and common in the neighboring Moscow Region that may be considered to be comparatively well-studied.

Material and Methods

A hand net was used for collecting. After a short collection trip made by me to the Kaluga Region (Iznoski District, Gamzyuki, June 29, 2010), 7 species were found in this locality. Mainly wet localities (except tree trunks *Medetera* was taken from) were explored. The collector of all specimens is the author of the paper; his name and the label data are omitted. Specimens examined in this study are deposited in the author's collection. The species are illustrated with ZEISS Discovery V-12 stereomicroscope and Axio-Cam MRc5 camera. General Distribution of species is given after Negrobov (1991) and Grichanov (2003–2010).

New records

Chrysotus cilipes Meigen, 1824 (Fig. 1)

Material examined. 1 ♀.

Distribution. Abkhazia, Afghanistan, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Czech, Estonia, Den-

Fig. 1. *Chrysotus cilipes* Meigen, male

mark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Madeira, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, N Russia: Leningrad, Novgorod, Pskov; C Russia: Moscow, Voronezh; S Russia: Adygea, Kabardino-Balkaria, Krasnodar, Rostov; E Russia: Tomsk, Altai, Krasnoyarsk, Baikal, Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Amur Reg., Primorskii Terr.; Slovakia, ?Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, UK, Ukraine, "Yugoslavia". Type locality: Germany: Hamburg.

***Dolichopus longicornis* Stannius, 1831 (Fig. 2)**

Material examined. 2♀.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, China, Czech, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Murmansk (Pechenga), Arkhangel'sk, Karelia, Komi, Leningrad, Vologda, Pskov, Novgorod; C Russia: Yaroslavl, Moscow, Perm, Lipetsk, Voronezh; S Russia: Krasnodar; E Russia: Irkutsk, Krasnoyarsk, Ural, Altai, Sayany, Amur Reg., Kamchatka, Magadan, Primorskii Terr., Sakhalin, Yakutia; Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine: Kherson, Carpathia; Nearctic: Canada: Yukon, USA: Alaska. Type locality: not given.

Fig. 2. *Dolichopus longicornis* Stannius, male.***Dolichopus simplex* Meigen, 1824 (Fig. 3)**

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Georgia, Hungary, Ireland, N Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, ?Romania, N Russia: Karelia, Murmansk, Leningrad, Vologda, Pskov, Novgorod; C Russia: Kirov, Nizhnii Novgorod, Moscow, Lipetsk, Voronezh; S Russia: Karachai-Cherkessia, Krasnodar, Rostov; E Russia: Orenburg, Yakutia; Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine: Cherkasy, Odessa. Type locality: Germany: Hamburg, Kiel.

Fig. 3. *Dolichopus simplex* Meigen, male.***Medetera jacula* (Fallén, 1823) (Fig. 4)**

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution. Armenia; Azerbaijan; Belarus, Belgium, Czech, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia; Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, N Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania; Russia: Adygea, Alania, Kabardino-Balkaria, Karelia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Velikii Novgorod, Orenburg, Penza, Perm, Pskov, Rostov, Samara, Stavropol, Volgograd, Vologda, Voronezh, Altai, Baikal, Buryatia, Urals; Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia; Turkey; UK, Ukraine: Crimea, Kharkiv, Kherson, Luhansk, Odessa, Poltava. Type locality: Sweden: Scania.

Fig. 4. *Medetera jacula* (Fallén), male.

***Campsicnemus curvipes* (Fallén, 1823) (Fig. 5)**

Material examined. 2 ♂, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Abkhazia, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Azores, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canary Is., Czech, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece incl. Crete; Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, ?Macedonia, Madeira, Morocco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia: Adygea, Alania, Dagestan, Kabardino-Balkaria, Karelia, Karachai-Cherkessia, Stavropol', Krasnodar, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Pskov, Ryazan, Vologda, Voronezh; Slovakia, ?Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, UK, Ukraine: Crimea, Odessa; "Yugoslavia". Type locality: not given.

Fig. 5. *Campsicnemus curvipes* (Fallén), male.

***Syntormon pumilus* (Meigen, 1824) (Fig. 6)**

Material examined. 1 ♂.

Distribution. Afghanistan, Armenia; Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech, Denmark, ?Egypt, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, ?Greece, Hungary, Ireland, ?Israel, Italy, Latvia, Morocco, Norway, Poland, Romania; Russia: Kabardino-Balkaria, Karelia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Murmansk, Pskov, Stavropol', Urals, Vologda, Voronezh; Slovakia, ?Slovenia, Sweden, Spain (Canary Is.), Tunisia, UK, Ukraine: Kherson, Odessa; "Yugoslavia"; Middle Asia [Some records may belong to *Syntormon denticulatus* (Zetterstedt, 1843) and should be confirmed]. Type locality: not given.

***Teuchophorus spinigerellus* (Zetterstedt, 1843) (Fig. 7)**

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀.

Distribution. Abkhazia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech, Denmark, Egypt; Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, S Kazakhstan,

Fig. 6. *Syntormon pumilus* (Meigen), male.

Fig. 7. *Teuchophorus spinigerellus* (Zetterstedt), male.

Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia: Adygea, Kabardino-Balkaria, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Pskov, Stavropol', Vologda; Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK. Type locality: Suecia meridionali & media, Scania ad Lund, Ostrogothia ad Wadstena, Dania [Sweden, Denmark].

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